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MODERN INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES AND THEIR CHARACTERISTICS IN ENGLISH TEACHING

Abstract: In this article, several methods of effective teaching of the English language, as well as some of the modern educational technologies used in language and its learning, are highlighted.

Keywords: Language, English, independent language learning, educational technologies, project, interest, activity, interactive methods.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini samarali o'qitishning bir qancha usullari, shuningdek, til va uni o'rganishda qo'llaniladigan ba'zi zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalari yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Til, ingliz tili, mustaqil til o'rganish, ta'lim texnologiyalari, loyiha, qiziqish, faollik, interfaol usullar.

Аннотация: В данной статье освещаются несколько методов эффективного обучения английскому языку, а также некоторые современные образовательные технологии, используемые при изучении языка.

Ключевые слова: Язык, английский язык, самостоятельное изучение языка, образовательные технологии, проект, интерес, деятельность, интерактивные методы.

Language: English

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INTRODUCTION

Today, the main focus is on the student, his personality and unique inner world. Therefore, the main goal of a modern teacher is to choose the methods and forms of organization of educational activities of students that optimally correspond to the set goal of personal development. In recent years, the issue of using new information technologies in schools has been raised more and more. It is not only new technical means, but also new forms and methods of teaching, a new approach to the educational process. The main goal of teaching foreign languages is to form and develop the communicative culture of schoolchildren, to teach them to practice a foreign language.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

Popular methods of teaching and learning English and Internet resources were used in the research process. During the writing of the article, the principles of theoretical deductive conclusion, analysis and synthesis, logicity were used.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The task of the teacher is to create conditions for practical mastery of the language for each student, to choose such teaching methods that allow each student to demonstrate his activity and creativity. The task of the teacher is to activate the cognitive activity of the student in the process of teaching foreign languages. Modern

pedagogical technologies, such as collaborative learning, project methodology, use of new information technologies, Internet resources, help to implement a person-oriented approach in the educational process, individualize and differentiate teaching, taking into account the abilities of children, their level of learning provides. Forms of working with computer training programs in foreign language classes include: learning vocabulary; practice pronunciation; teaching dialogic and monologic speech; teaching writing; development of grammatical events.

The possibilities of using Internet resources are enormous. The global Internet creates conditions for students and teachers located anywhere in the world to obtain any necessary information: regional geographical materials, news from the life of young people, articles from newspapers and magazines, etc.

Using the Internet in English lessons can solve a number of didactic problems: forming reading skills and competencies using global network materials; improving the writing skills of schoolchildren; replenishing students' vocabulary; forming students' motivation to learn English. In addition, this work is aimed at exploring the possibilities of Internet technologies for expanding the horizons of schoolchildren, establishing and maintaining business relationships and contacts with their peers in English-speaking countries. Students can take part in tests, quizzes, competitions, Olympiads held on the Internet, participate in correspondence, conversations, video

conferences, etc. with their peers in other countries.

Students can get information about a problem they are currently working on in a project.

The substantive foundations of mass computerization are connected with the fact that a modern computer is an effective means of optimizing the conditions of mental labor, in general, any of its manifestations. The computer has one characteristic that is most apparent when used as a tool for teaching others and as an aid in acquiring knowledge, and that is its inanimate nature. The machine may be "friendly" to the user and may "support" him at times, but it will never show signs of annoyance or let you feel bored. In this sense, the use of computers is perhaps most useful in individualizing some aspects of teaching. The main goal of learning a foreign language at school is the formation of communicative competence, all other goals (education, training, development) are realized in the process of implementing this main goal. The communicative approach involves teaching communication and the formation of the ability to interact intercultural, which is the basis of Internet activity. The Internet has no meaning outside of communication - it is an international multinational, intercultural society, the life of which is based on the electronic communication of millions of people around the world, talking at the same time - this is the largest conversation in terms of the number and volume of participants that has ever taken place. By participating in a lesson on a foreign language, we create a real model of communication.

Currently, priority is given to issues of communication, interactivity, authenticity of

communication, language learning in a cultural context, autonomy and humanism of education. These principles allow the development of intercultural competence as a component of communicative competence. The ultimate goal of teaching foreign languages is to teach free orientation in a foreign language environment and the ability to adequately respond to various situations, i.e. communication. Today, new methods using Internet resources are challenging traditional foreign language teaching. To teach communication in a foreign language, you need to create authentic, real-life situations that stimulate learning of the material and develop adequate behavior (this is called the principle of communicative authenticity). New technologies, in particular the Internet, are trying to correct this error. The communicative approach is a strategy that simulates communication, aimed at consciously understanding the material and methods of working with it, creating psychological and linguistic readiness for communication. Implementing a communicative approach on the Internet is not particularly difficult for the user. The communicative task should invite students to discuss a problem or question, students not only exchange information, but also evaluate it. The main criterion that allows us to distinguish this approach from other types of educational activities is that students independently select linguistic units to formulate their own opinions. In the communicative approach, the use of the Internet is highly encouraged: its goal is to interest students in learning a foreign language by accumulating and expanding their knowledge and experience.

One of the main requirements for teaching foreign languages using Internet resources is to create interaction in the lesson, which is usually called interactivity in methodology. Interactivity is "the unification, coordination and complementarity of efforts in the communicative goal and result using speech tools." By teaching real language, the Internet helps to develop speaking skills and abilities, and also ensures genuine interest in teaching vocabulary and grammar, and therefore efficiency. Interactivity not only creates real-life situations, but also forces students to respond to them adequately in a foreign language.

One of the technologies that provide student-centered learning is the project method as a way to develop creativity, cognitive activity and independence. The typology of projects is diverse. Projects can be divided into monoprojects, collective, oral, concrete, written and Internet projects. In real practice, it is often necessary to deal with mixed projects, which have research, creative, practice-oriented and informative characters. Project work is a multifaceted approach to language learning, covering reading, listening, speaking and grammar. The project method helps to develop active independent thinking of students and directs them to joint research work. In my opinion, project-based learning teaches children to cooperate, and learning to cooperate fosters moral values such as mutual assistance and the ability to empathize, forms creativity and activates students. In general, the inseparability of teaching and learning is observed in the project learning process.

The project method develops students' communication skills, culture of communication, the ability to concisely and

easily formulate thoughts, tolerance of the opinions of communication partners, the ability to obtain information from various sources, process it using modern computer technologies, and creates a language environment that contributes to the emergence of a natural need for communication in a foreign language.

The project form of work is one of the most relevant technologies that allows students to apply the knowledge gained on the subject. Students expand their horizons, the boundaries of language knowledge, gain experience in its practical use, learn to listen and hear speech in a foreign language, and understand each other when defending projects. Children work with reference books, dictionaries, and computers, thereby creating the opportunity for direct contact with the real language, which does not provide language learning in the classroom using only textbooks.

Project work is a creative process. The student, independently or under the guidance of a teacher, seeks a solution to a problem, which requires not only knowledge of the language, but also a large amount of subject knowledge, creative, communicative and intellectual skills.

In the process of foreign languages, the project method can be used within the framework of program materials on almost any subject. Working on projects develops imagination, fantasy, creative thinking, independence and other personal qualities.

TO modern technologies also apply collaborative technology. The main idea is to create conditions for active joint activity of students in various learning environments. Children are grouped into groups of 3-4, given a single task, and the role of each is discussed.

Each student is responsible not only for the result of his work, but also for the result of the whole group. Therefore, weak students try to figure out what they do not understand from weak ones, and strong students try to help weak ones understand the task thoroughly. And the whole class benefits from this, because the gaps are closed together.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The introduction of information technologies into education significantly diversifies the process of perceiving and processing information. Thanks to computers, the Internet and multimedia, students have a unique opportunity to assimilate large amounts of information with subsequent analysis and sorting. The motivational basis of educational activities is also expanding significantly. In the

context of the use of multimedia, students receive information from newspapers, television, conduct interviews themselves, and hold teleconferences.

In language portfolio technology, the main criteria for assessing the level of foreign language proficiency are tests. The priority of this technology is to shift the educational process from teacher to student. The student, in turn, is consciously responsible for the results of his/her cognitive activity. The above technology leads to the gradual formation of students' skills in independent assimilation of information. In general, the language portfolio is multifunctional and contributes to the development of multilingualism.

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